

Microbiological Quality of Recreation Waters: A Case Study at Oba Community in Anambra State

Awari, V.G.^{1*}, Nwozor, N. C.², Oghonim, P. AN³, Ogbonna U.S.A.², Egurefa, S.O.⁴, Ogujiofor, F.I.², Abana, C.C.², Soludo, O.C.², Imo, K.I.⁵, Chukwu A.U.¹, Awah, N.S.², and Kaliku, M.O.¹.

¹Department of Microbiology, Tansian University, Umunya, Anambra, Nigeria

²Department of Applied Microbiology, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, P.M.B. 5025 Awka, Nigeria

³Microbiology Department, Biological Sciences, University of Delta, Agbor P.M.B 2090, Agbor, Delta State, Nigeria.

⁴Department of Science Laboratory Technology, Southern delta University PMB 05, Ozoro Delta State, Nigeria

⁵Department of Medical Laboratory Science, Tansian University, Umunya, Anambra, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

Swimming pool water users can be exposed to a range of disease-causing microorganisms and pose public health concerns. This study was aimed at assessing the microbiological quality of swimming pool waters from Oba community in Anambra State. Three swimming pool water samples including control sample were collected from different swimming pools situated at Oba community in Anambra State and transported at once to the Microbiology laboratory for microbiological analyses. The results of the total heterotrophic bacterial counts of the water samples from control sample water to swimming pool sample waters ranged from 0.21×10^4 CFU/ml to 5.5×10^4 CFU/ml, total coliform count ranged from 0.00×10^4 CFU/ml to 3.4×10^4 CFU/ml and total fungal count ranged from 0.00×10^4 CFU/ml to 2.7×10^4 CFU/ml. From the results, the microbial counts of the swimming pool water was higher, compared to that of the control water sample. The microbial isolates included bacteria and fungi as follows; *Streptococcus* spp., *Staphylococcus* spp., *Pseudomonas* spp., *Proteus* spp., *Klebsiella* spp., *Escherichia* spp, *Aspergillus* spp. and *Mucor* spp. From the results, *Klebsiella* spp. and *Pseudomonas* spp. frequently occurred in the samples. This study therefore revealed the potential health risk associated with use of swimming pool recreational water facilities without adequate treatment. The presence of pathogenic organisms in swimming pool waters could pose a lot of harm to humans who get in contact with them. These pathogenic organisms in one way or the other, recreational water finds its way into the body through the mouth and could cause variety of microbial diseases like; gastrointestinal illnesses, diarrhea, vomiting, nausea, stomachache, sore throat, cough, runny nose, cold, fever, rashes or itchy skin, eye infection, upper respiratory illnesses (URI) etc. It is recommended that when using swimming pool, water users should avoid swallowing the water, regardless of the water quality and should take a shower immediately after

swimming and also, should avoid swimming when sustained with open sores or wounds in order to avoid contact with pathogenic organisms associated with the swimming pool waters and its surrounding environment.

Key words: *Microbiological quality, Pathogenic organisms, Public health concerns Recreational water, Surrounding environment.*

Introduction

Recreational water refers to rivers, lakes, and coastal waters that are used for recreational purposes (USEPA, 2015). Recreational water includes water in swimming pools, hot tubs, waterparks, interactive fountains, water play areas, lakes, rivers or oceans used for surfing, swimming, fishing, boating, etc. (Yoder et al., 2008). Recreational water can become contaminated with pathogens like bacteria, fungi, and viruses from human sewage and animal manure. The growth of several bacteria in contaminated water can make it injurious for our health and environment (Yoder et al., 2008). Other activities carried out around recreational waters include activities such as hiking, nature viewing, and hunting waterfowl (DENR, 2019).

Water quality can be described as a combination of sanitary inspection and microbial water quality assessment. In developing countries, the quality of water is very essential to public health. Literatures have shown that there are numerous types of microbial pathogens found in the recreational areas (Hervio-Health et al., 2002; Egurefa et al., 2024; Ezeokoli et al., 2023; Awari et al., 2023; Victor-Aduloju et al., 2023; Agu et al., 2023) and this can thus, serve as a vehicle for the transmission of microbial diseases to people by contact with contaminated water. The primary contact with recreational water involves activity such as swimming, windsurfing, and waterskiing and secondary contact involve boating and fishing. Contamination of water with fecal bacteria is a common and persistent problem impacting public health, local and national economies. Coffey et al., (2014) stated clearly that one of the major reasons for contamination of the recreational waters is the increasing number of population in the cities and metropolis as well as, the uncontrolled discharge of human waste, animal and industrial sewage and other various domestic wastes into the water bodies results to environmental damage and eutrophication of the recreational waters and its environments (Wade et al., 2006). The presence of pathogenic agents, such as *E. coli*, *Salmonella*, *Shigella*, and *Campylobacter* can cause waterborne diseases and it has been reported worldwide. The identification of the occurrence of diseases which may be transmitted by recreational water contact has also been reported (Russel and Walling, 2007). Pathogenic microorganisms are found among indigenous communities (e.g., cyanobacteria, protozoa, vibrios) and are introduced into waters in various ways (Carbral, 2010; Cayabol et al., 2021). Some of these infectious microorganisms are autochthonous to freshwater environments (*Aeromonas hydrophila*, *Naegleria fowleri*, *Legionella pneumophila*) and to marine and brackish waters (e.g., *Vibrio cholerae* and other vibrios, *Aeromonas* spp.) may represent natural reservoirs of many types of pathogenic microorganisms in recreational waters and their environments

(Pandey et al., 2014). Primarily, the bacteria like *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella*, *Vibrio*, and *Shigella* found in intestinal tracts of humans and warm-blooded animals can enter the water through feces thereby making the water fatal for consumption. Moreover, the intestinal tracts of warmblooded animals carry viruses like rotavirus; enterovirus etc. which contaminates water and makes it unsafe for use (Gibson, 2014). These contaminants can gain entry into recreational waters through point source discharge; coming from single source like pipe and refuse and though non-point source pollution; where contaminants leach into a water source across a wider area (Barnett et al., 2018). These recreational waters are mainly associated particularly with agricultural production (Harrington et al., 1993). Fecal matter from livestock can get into waterways in several ways like: rainfall washing livestock effluent from the land into waterways, livestock defecating directly into waterways when they have access, and leaching into groundwater. Bacterial levels in waterways are often highest after rainfall, when fecal matter is carried from land into waterways (Ackerman and Weisberg, 2003).

Recreational water illnesses are microbial diseases that people can contact through contaminated water they swim in and play in, like: pools, hot tubs, water playgrounds, oceans, lakes, and rivers. If the water is contaminated with germs, the most common symptoms are diarrhea, skin rashes, ear pain, cough or congestion, and eye pain (Pruss, 1998). For these reasons recreational waters must be monitored for microbial quality so that safety measure can be carried out to guarantee water quality in order to prevent or reduce the possibilities of disease outbreak so that there will be no risk for human and environmental health hazard (Coffey et al., 2014). Hence, the present study is aimed at determining the microbiological quality of some recreational water in Port Harcourt, where bacterial and fungal population in the recreational water samples were enumerated in order to evaluate the risk associated with the use of contaminated recreational water.

This paper aims to ascertain the microbiological quality of selected swimming pool waters in Oba community in Anambra State, Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Sample Collection

Two swimming pool water samples including control sample were collected from different swimming pools located at Oba community in Anambra State adopting standard methods according to Abana., (2024); Ogbuleka *et al.*, (2024); and transported at once to the Microbiology laboratory for microbiological analyses.

Sterilization of Materials

Test tubes, conical flask, pipettes, petri dishes, beaker and culture medium (those requiring) were sterilized by autoclaving at 121⁰C at 15lbs for 15 minutes. Test tubes, pipettes and Petri dishes

were also sterilized by dry oven in the laboratory at a temperature of 15⁰C for 1 hour before use. The work bench was sterilized with pads soaked in isopropyl alcohol.

Procedures for Microbiology Analysis

Serial Dilution

From the homogenized preparation, 1 ml was transferred to test tube 1 (containing 9 ml of water) using sterile pipette and mixed thoroughly. 1ml from test tube 1 was transferred to test tube 2 using a sterile pipette. This procedure continued until test tube 5. The content of test tube 5 (10⁻⁵) served as the inoculum.

Procedure for Total Bacterial Count

The spread plate method was used. 9ml of sterile normal saline solution was distributed in five test tubes for serial dilution. The test tubes were sterilized by autoclaving at 121⁰C for 15 minutes after which 1ml of the swimming pool water sample was transferred into the tube containing 9ml normal saline using sterile pipette to make the tenfold serial dilution. The first tube gave 10⁻¹ dilution, subsequent tenfold serial dilutions were prepared up to 10⁻⁵.

Using a sterile 1ml pipette, 0.1ml from 10⁻³ and 10⁻⁵ dilution were transferred aseptically onto the surface of solid nutrient agar, MacConkey agar, SS agar, EMB agar, PDA plates. Each dilution was plated in duplicate. The inoculum were evenly spread over the surface of the medium using sterile bent glass rods. The glass rods was sterilized by dipping into 70% alcohol and flaming, and then allowed to cool. The plates were then inverted and incubated at 25⁰C for 9 hours for fungi and 37⁰C for 24hours for bacteria's. The total viable count was calculated using the formula:

Total viable count (CFU/ml) =

$N/V \times D$,

where

N = mean colony,

V = volume plate

D = Dilution and expressed as colony forming unit per ml (cfu/ml).

Total Coliform Determination

A tenfold serial dilution of the sample was made with diluents (physiological saline). An aliquot (0.1ml) from the 10⁻⁵ was seeded onto Mac-conkey agar and incubated for 18-24 hours at 37⁰C.

Isolation (of Pure Culture)

Zero point one (0.1ml) of the inoculum (10⁻⁵) was poured into the media's and spread evenly on it with the aid of a sterile glass spreader. The plate was allowed to dry for 15 minutes. The plates were incubated at 35⁰C for 24 hours (1days). The same were done for all media. An uninoculated agar plate of both nutrient agar, MacConkey agar, SS agar, and EMB agar served as control.

After the incubation period, the plates were brought out of the incubators and the colonies were counted using a colony counter device and each count was expressed in colony forming unit per ml (cfuml⁻¹).

Pure culture were obtained by sub culturing the different colonies into nutrient agar plate via streaking method. The plates were incubated at 35°C for 24 hours (1days).

Identification of Bacteria Isolates

The identification of organisms was done based on their cultural characteristics, colonial morphology, Gram staining and biochemical profile.

Microscopic Examination

Gram staining was carried out for each pure culture in the Petri dish. This helps to distinguish between Gram positive and Gram negative bacteria. A thin smear of the isolates were made on different slides with the aid of a wire loop and left to dry and after they were heat fixed and allowed to cool. Then the different smears were covered with crystal violet stain for 60 seconds and rapidly washed off with clean water. Then the smears were covered with Lugol's iodine for 60 seconds and rapidly washed off with clean water. The smears were decolorized rapidly with alcohol and washed out immediately with clean water. Then the smears were covered with safaranine for 60 seconds and washed immediately with clean water. The stained smears were then allowed to air-dry. After drying, a drops of oil immersion were dropped on the stained smears and viewed with the aid of a microscope ($\times 100$ oil objective lens) to check for the microscopic properties of the organisms like the Gram reaction, morphology (Cheesbrough, 2006).

Biochemical Test

The methods of Calaresu (2013) was employed for the identification of the bacteria isolates. The biochemical tests that were used to further characterize the bacteria are catalase, methyl-red, oxidase, citrate utilization, and coagulase and indole tests. Oxidase test was also carried out on the Gram negative isolates to know if they are oxidase positive or negative. The identities of coliforms and bacteria were then confirmed using the identification aid outlined in Bergey's Manual for Determinative Bacteriology (Holt *et al.*, 1994).

Catalase test

Small inoculums of bacterial isolate was mixed into hydrogen peroxide solution (3%) and the rapid elaboration of oxygen bubbles occurs (positive). The lack of catalase is evident by a lack of or weak bubble production.

Oxidase test

To test the production of oxidase bacteria. The bacteria isolates were placed on a filter paper impregnated with 2 drops of 1% oxidase reagent. Observe for change in color. Purple coloration indicates positive. No color change indicates negative.

Indole test

The indole test screens for the ability of an organism to degrade the amino acid tryptophan and produce indole, pyritic acid and ammonia after incubating at 35°C for 48 hrs in peptone water. The test organism was inoculated into tryptophan broth, which contain tryptophan. KOVACs reagent was used to detect the indole produced. Cherry red coloration indicates positive.

Citrate test

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Determines the ability of microorganisms to utilize citrate as the sole source of carbon and as energy source for the growth and ammonium salt as a sole source of nitrogen. Simmon citrate agar was inoculated with isolates and incubated at 35⁰C for 48 hrs. Blue coloration indicates positive.

Methyl Red Test

To determine the ability of microorganisms to oxidize glucose with the production and stabilization of high concentrations of acid end products. Isolates were inoculated on methyl red broth at 37⁰C for 48hrs after which 5ml of the methyl indicator was added. Red coloration indicates positive. Yellow indicates negative.

Motility Test

A drop of the suspension was placed on a slide and covered with a cover slip. Hanging drop preparation was achieved by placing a drop of the suspension on a cover slip and inverting this over a cavity slide. Then the preparation sealed with molten jelly to prevent it from drying out. preparation was examined microscopically for motile organism using ×10 and ×40 objective lens. The movement of the bacterium was shown when the organism moves itself in different directions or in a single direction. When this occurred, the mobility test of the organism is positive.

Voges Proskauer Test

This test is used to determine organisms such as members of the *Klebsiella-Enterobacter-Hafnia-Serratia* group produce acetoin as the chief end product of glucose metabolism and form smaller quantities of mixed acids. In the presence of atmospheric oxygen and 40% potassium hydroxide, acetoin is converted to diacetyl and alpha-naphthol serves as a catalyst to bring out red complex.

Inoculate a tube of MR/VP broth with a pure culture of the test organism. Incubate for 24 hours at 35⁰C. At the end of this time, aliquot 1ml of broth to clean test-tube. Add 0.6ml of 5% alpha naphthol, followed by 0.2ml of 40% KOH. (Note: It is essential that the reagents be added in this order). Shake the tube gently to expose the medium to atmospheric oxygen and allow the tube to remain undisturbed for 10 to 15 minutes. A positive test is represented by the development of a red color 15 minutes or more after the addition of the reagents indicating the presence of diacetyl, the oxidation product of acetoin.

Sugar Fermentation

This test was carried out to test the ability of the isolate to ferment sugars. Glucose, sucrose, D-manitol, and maltose were used. The sugars were added to a basal medium (peptone water base) to which colour change from blue to yellow indicated acid production, empty space at the bottom of the durham tube indicated gas production while no colour indicates negative change Bromothimol blue indicator was then added to detect change in pH, which develops during growth.

The sugar was prepared as 10% solution. The sugar gave 1% fermentable substrate when added to the basal medium. They were then dispensed into tubes and Durham tubes were inserted into

each tube to detect the presence of gas production during growth. The tube was then sterilized in the autoclave at 115°C for 10 minutes, cooled and inoculated with the isolate. The tubes were incubated for 24-48 hours at 37°C.

Fungal Sub-Culturing

The discrete colonies on the pour plate were picked with a sterile loop and streaked on Petri dishes containing solidified medium. The organisms were sub-cultured onto new plate several times until pure culture was obtained.

Identification of Fungal Isolates

This was carried out by wet mount and slide culture method as described by Larone (1995).

Wet Mount

A drop of 70% alcohol was added onto a clean microscope slide and with a sterile platinum wire loop, a colony from the isolate was transferred onto the drop of the 70% alcohol on the slide. Before the alcohol dried out one drop of the lactophenol cotton blue was added and the slide was covered using a cover slip. The slide were then taken for microscope examination using an objective (40x) of the light microscope.

Slide Culture

This was done to observe the morphological characteristics of the isolates without disturbing the arrangement of spore hyphae. A 100mm square agar block (PDA) each were placed on sterile slides. The slides were incubated with speck of fungal colony and aseptically Petri dish containing small amounts of water helped to prevent the agar from drying out. The Petri dishes were covered and incubated at 25-30°C. Viable growth was examined at intervals when the viable growth was observed, the cover slip were removed and the lactophenol cotton blue mount was performed and examined microscopically for sporulation.

Results

The total heterotrophic bacteria, coliform and fungal counts of the swimming pool samples were recorded as follows 5.5×10^4 to 4.0×10^4 in Nutrient Agar, while the total coliform count ranged between 3.4×10^4 to 2.0×10^4 in MacConkey Agar, the total fungal count ranged between 2.7×10^3 to 2.5×10^3 in PDA. The bacterial isolates includes *Streptococcus* spp., *Staphylococcus* spp., *Pseudomonas* spp., *Proteus* spp., *Klebsiella* spp., *Escherichia* spp, while the fungal isolates were *Aspergillus* spp and *Mucor* spp. The total microbial counts of the samples were shown in table 4.1 below, the presence of suspected microorganisms in the recreational water samples were shown in table 4.2, the biochemical identification of bacteria isolated from the recreational water samples were shown in table 4.3 while the characteristics of fungal isolates were shown in in table 4.4.

Table 4.1: Microbial Counts of the Recreational Water Samples

PARAMETER TESTED (cfu/ml)	CONTROL SAMPLE	SAMPLE CODE CSP	SAMPLE CODE SSP	
Total Heterotrophic Bacterial Count	0.1 x 10 ⁴	4.0 x 10 ⁴	5.5 x 10 ⁴	NA
Total Coliform Count	0.00 x 10 ⁴	2.0 x 10 ⁴	3.4 x 10 ⁴	MAC
<i>E. coli</i> Count	0.00 x 10 ⁴	0.00 x 10 ⁴	1.0 x 10 ⁴	
Total Fungal Count	0.00 x 10 ⁴	2.5 x 10 ³	2.7 x 10 ³	PDA

Key:

CSP = Chibon Swimming Pool
 SSP = Sinachi Swimming Pool

Table 4.2: Presence of Suspected Microorganisms in the Recreational Water Samples

ISOLATE	CSP	SSP
<i>Streptomyces spp</i>	√	√
<i>Staphylococcus spp</i>	√	√
<i>Proteus spp</i>	O	√
<i>Escherichia spp</i>	O	√
<i>Klebsiella spp</i>	O	√
<i>Pseudomonas spp</i>	√	√
<i>Aspergillus spp</i>	√	√
<i>Mucor spp</i>	O	√

Key:

O = Absent
 √ = Present

Table 4.3: BIOCHEMICAL IDENTIFICATION OF BACTERIA ISOLATED FROM THE RECREATIONAL WATER SAMPLES

S/ N	Code	Colour	Shape	Elevation	Opacity	Margin	Size	Texture	Gram RXN	Shape	Catalase	Oxidase	Motility	Citrate	Indole	MR	VP	Glucose	Lactose
1	CSP	Pale	Circular	Flat	Opaque	Entire	Large	Moist	-ve	Rod	-	+	-	+	+	-	-	+	+
2	SSP	Creamy	Circular	Raised	Translucent	Wavy	Small	Mucoid	-ve	Rod	-	+	+	-	+	-	+	-	+
3	CSP	Milky	Round	Elevated	Translucent	Entire	Small	Mucoid	+ve	Cocci	+	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	-
4	SSP	Creamy	Circular	Flat	Opaque	Entire	Small	Moist	-ve	Rod	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	+
5	CSP	Bluegreen	Round	Flat	Opaque	Entire	Large	Moist	-ve	Rod	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
6	SSP	Pale Yellow	Round	Elevated	Translucent	Entire	Small	Butter	-ve	Rod	-	-	+	+	-	+	-	+	-

KEY = (-) = Negative
 (+) = Positive
 CSP = Chibon Swimming Pool
 SSP = Sinachi Swimming Pool

Table 4.4: Macroscopic and Microscopic Characteristics of Fungi Isolated From the Recreational Water Samples

No	Culture characteristics	Microscopic characteristics	Probable Organisms
1 CSP	Dark grey cottony colonies, fluffy-white on reverse side, whitish gray center surrounded by sporulating mycelia	Non-septate hyphae with, long branched sporangium containing collumella without rhizoid	<i>Mucor spp</i>
2 SSP	Blue-green velvety growth with white periphery and reserve white colour	Septate hyphae with branched conidiospores arranged in chains	<i>Penicillium spp</i>

Key:

CSP = Chibon Swimming Pool
 SSP = Sinachi Swimming Pool

Discussion

Water-based recreation is of vital importance to human life. The results of the total heterotrophic bacterial counts of the water samples from control sample water to swimming pool sample waters ranged from 0.21×10^4 CFU/ml to 5.5×10^4 CFU/ml, total coliform count ranged from 0.00×10^4 CFU/ml to 3.4×10^4 CFU/ml and total fungal count ranged from 0.00×10^4 CFU/ml to 2.7×10^4 CFU/ml. From the results, the microbial counts of the swimming pool water was higher, compared to that of the control water sample. The microbial isolates included bacteria and fungi as follows; *Streptococcus* spp., *Staphylococcus* spp., *Pseudomonas* spp., *Proteus* spp., *Klebsiella* spp., *Escherichia coli*, *Aspergillus* spp. and *Mucor*. From the results, *Klebsiella* spp. and *Pseudomonas* spp. frequently occurred in the samples. This study therefore revealed the potential health risk associated with use of swimming pool recreational water facilities without adequate treatment. The presence of pathogenic organisms in swimming pool waters could pose a lot of harm to humans who get in contact with them. Nevertheless, literatures have recorded that mortality rate is twice among the non-swimmers than the active swimmers (Chase *et al.*, 2008; Anciaes *et al.*, 2020; Amadi-Ikpa, C. N. and Awari, V. G. 2023). Water-based recreation is always enjoyable when compared to non-water related adventures (Barnett *et al.*, 2018) and critical antidotes for several persistent ailments including arthritis through enhance utilization of affected bodily parts devoid of aggravating pains (Wade *et al.*, 2006). In spite of its usefulness, recreational water bodies in general, are always vulnerable to various forms of pollutants. Polluted water is not healthy for drinking, bathing, industry, agriculture (Boelee *et al.*, 2019) as well as its fitness for swimming and other recreational activities (Boelee *et al.*, 2019).

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Monitoring the number of indicator microorganisms such as fecal coliform and *E. coli* is a common approach to quantifying pathogenic microorganisms present in the surface waters (Cabral, 2010; Pandey *et al.*, 2014; Cimatu, 2020). The safety of recreational water is an important and timely issue when dealing with public health and sustainable water management (Ahmed, *et al.*, 2010). The results of this present study showed that recreational waters harbour a number of pathogenic microorganisms. This may be due to a number of factors including: the high number of different users, the various sources of water, discharge from municipal waste waters, contamination from bathers, discharge from onsite toilet facilities and boats etc. (Caruso *et al.*, 2002). According to Hellein *et al.*, (2011) the swimming pools having bacterial and fungal isolates were those facilities that are being frequently used, not changed and also not treated with purifying agents such as chlorine.

The potential health problems posed by waterborne microorganisms are difficult to eradicate through conventional means of disinfecting (Awari V. G., 2023). Among the list of such bacteria and fungi are; *Streptococcus* specie, *Staphylococcus* specie, *Pseudomonas* specie, *Proteus spp*, *Klebsiella* specie, *Escherichia coli*, *Mucor spp* and *Aspergillus* specie. Similar findings have been reported by researchers including; Mansoorian *et al.*, (2013); Hutcheson *et al.*, (2013); Abana, C. C. *et al.*, (2024); Anazodo, C.A, *et al.*, (2024). The study therefore shows the potential health risk associated with use of these water recreational facilities and that *Klebsiella* specie and *Pseudomonas* specie are the most frequently encountered isolates. Hence, suggest that there is a need for monitoring of recreational waters because they are pathogenic organisms that could pose a lot of harm to humans who get in contact with them.

This work is similar to work done by Bouzid, (2016) who isolated eight clinically important pathogenic bacteria including: *Escherichia coli*, *Proteus mirabilis*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Shigella sp.*, *Salmonella sp.*, *Vibrio parahaemolyticus* and *V. cholera* from contaminated recreational waters. They further emphasized that the presence of these bacteria in recreational water is alarming because the waterborne pathogens can cause illness with severe outbreak of microbial diseases when come in contact with to the average population (Franco, 2009; WHO 2015). In previous studies carried out by several researches like: Russel and Walling, (2007); Byappanahalli *et al.*, (2012); USEPA, (2023); Boehm and Sassoubre, (2014); revealed that microorganisms associated with contaminated recreational waters included; bacteria, protozoa and viruses. Furthermore, Byappanahalli *et al.*, (2012); Pandey *et al.*, (2014); USEPA, (2015); Bouzid (2016) reported clearly that, these pathogenic microorganisms have been identified as the primary source of microbiological water contamination and are usually responsible for waterborne microbial diseases such as typhoid fever, hepatitis, cholera and poses environmental and public health risk (Boehm and Sassoubre, 2014).

Conclusion

Contaminated swimming pool water has been known to cause variety of microbial diseases because in one way or the other, swimming pool water finds its way into the body through the mouth. These diseases may include: gastrointestinal illnesses including the following: diarrhea

(three or more loose stools in a 24-hour period), vomiting, nausea, stomachache, sore throat, cough, runny nose, cold, or fever, rashes or itchy skin, eye infection, upper respiratory illnesses (URI) and many more. From this research, it is suspected that the high microbial count seen in recreational water samples including: AR and DR might be as a result of the household wastes disposed in the water. This is because household wastes mixed in garbage can result to environments that are naturally conducive for the multiplication of microorganisms. The safety of recreational waters is an important and timely issue especially as regards to public health sustainable water management. The number of hazardous microorganisms and their forms present in the recreational water is large and the regulatory agencies approach is guided by fecal contamination events. The quality of recreational water in many Nigerian cities cannot be neglected because of the risk and implications to human health. Hence, the prime motivation for carrying out this study is to assess the quality of recreational waters in order to ascertain the negative effects of the use of contaminated recreational water poses on human health.

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